

Microstructure, chemistry, phase composition, and stress-induced transformability of abnormal grains in DC flash sintered 3 mol% yttria-stabilized zirconia

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Abstract

Abnormal grain growth was triggered by DC flash sintering in 3 mol% yttria-stabilised zirconia (3YSZ). The abnormal grains exceeded 100 μm in size and exhibited a tetragonal structure, as confirmed by X-ray diffraction and Raman spectroscopy. No spontaneous transformation to the monoclinic phase was observed in the sintered samples. Transmission electron microscopy revealed that the abnormal grains consisted of thin Y-lean and Y-rich lamellae, similar to those previously reported in the early stages of high-temperature decomposition of the non-transformable tetragonal (t') phase in zirconia with higher yttria contents. Electrochemically reduced 3YSZ is considered to mimic the behaviour of zirconia compositions with higher yttria contents. The coherency and small domain size of the lamellar structure provide additional stability, preventing spontaneous transformation of the abnormal grains to the monoclinic polymorph. Nevertheless, it is shown that transformation to the monoclinic phase can still be triggered by stress associated with an indentation crack.

1. Introduction

Pure zirconia is a polymorphic material that, under standard conditions, undergoes transitions from a monoclinic (*m*) phase (stable at room temperature up to ~ 1170 °C) to a tetragonal (*t*) phase (stable between ~ 1170 °C and ~ 2370 °C), and finally to a cubic (*c*) phase (stable above ~ 2370 °C up to the melting point) [1]. When doped with 3 mol% of Y_2O_3 , the phase stability is altered. The *t* phase can be retained metastably at room temperature, enabling the transformation toughening phenomenon that significantly enhances fracture resistance [1,2]. This makes 3 mol% of yttria-stabilized zirconia (3YSZ) a versatile material in a wide range of applications where a high mechanical strength, fracture toughness, and chemical inertness are required [3].

The stability of the *t* phase in 3YSZ at room temperature also depends on grain size, which must remain below approximately $1 \mu m$ [1,4,5]. If tetragonal grains stabilized by 3 mol% of Y_2O_3 exceed the micrometre size range, spontaneous tetragonal to monoclinic ($t \rightarrow m$) transformation occurs upon cooling to room temperature. Nowadays, obtaining a metastable microstructure is not difficult due to the availability of nanometric 3YSZ powders, relatively slow grain growth kinetics hindered by a solute-drag mechanism, and no tendency to abnormal grain growth (AGG) during conventional sintering [6,7].

The advent of flash sintering (FS) technology has introduced new challenges and opportunities for tailoring the microstructure of 3YSZ ceramics [8–10]. Flash sintering uses either alternating current (AC) or direct current (DC) to rapidly heat a ceramic powder compact by means of Joule heating [11–13]. A notable advantage of FS is the extremely rapid densification, with samples reaching high density within seconds. To perform flash sintering of 3YSZ, a powder compact is connected to a power supply (typically via metallic electrodes). Because 3YSZ is an electrical insulator at room temperature, it has to be preheated to achieve sufficient ionic conductivity to initiate the process [14,15].

After a voltage is applied to the electrodes, an electric current flows through the circuit. The electrical charge carriers are of two types: oxygen ions in the 3YSZ sample and electrons in the metallic electrodes, which results in electrochemical reactions at the electrode-sample interfaces. These reactions include incorporation of atmospheric oxygen into the 3YSZ sample at the cathode and release of oxygen from the sample at the anode interface [16]. Under high DC currents, the rate of oxygen incorporation at the cathode may become insufficient, leading to local oxygen depletion. As a consequence, oxygen

vacancies, which migrate in the opposite direction to oxygen ions, accumulate near the cathode [17]. This process, known as electrochemical blackening, manifests as a colour change of the 3YSZ material from white to black [18]. The effect results from a reduction of the bandgap [17–20], which increases the electronic contribution to the overall electrical conductivity of 3YSZ.

Electrochemical reduction during DC flash sintering also significantly influences diffusion rates and grain growth. Several studies have shown that grain growth in the electrochemically reduced regions of the specimen can be accelerated by up to three orders of magnitude [21–24]. Some studies also reported exaggerated grain growth in the vicinity of the electrodes, attributed to local overheating or melting caused by high contact resistance [25,26]. In our previous study [27], however, we showed that increasing the DC load can also induce AGG away from the electrodes, resulting in abnormal grains tens of micrometres in size embedded within a submicron-grained matrix.

The phase composition of DC flash sintered yttria-stabilized zirconia has also been investigated extensively [28–31]. These studies indicate that new phases, distinct from the original phase, may form during DC flash sintering. These phases are associated with reduction during flash sintering and revert to the original *t* phase of 3YSZ [28–30] or the original *c* phase of 8YSZ [31] via re-oxidation once the current is switched off in air. Interestingly, Dong et al. [21] obtained very large (~50 μm) tetragonal grains in electrochemically reduced samples. The authors proposed several mechanisms that could be responsible for preventing spontaneous *t* \rightarrow *m* transformation such as an abundance of oxygen vacancies and/or partial reduction of Zr^{4+} to Zr^{3+} .

In the present study, 3YSZ samples were subjected to DC flash sintering in air at a relatively high current density of 190 mA/mm^2 in order to intentionally induce AGG, leading to the formation of abnormal tetragonal grains embedded within a fine-grained 3YSZ matrix. The primary objective was to investigate the chemistry and phase composition of these abnormal grains at the sub-grain level. Particular attention was paid to their local chemical heterogeneity, nano-scale structure, and susceptibility to stress-induced transformation. The behaviour of these grains under external mechanical loading was evaluated and compared with that of the surrounding matrix. This work provides new insights into the microstructural origin of the enhanced stability of the *t* phase in abnormal grains and demonstrates that this stabilization

is not absolute, as these grains can still undergo transformation under external stimuli such as applied stress. The findings have broader implications for the controlled design of flash sintered zirconia ceramics with tailored mechanical properties.

2. Experimental

Commercially available 3YSZ powder with binder (TZ-3YB, Tosoh Corp.) was uniaxially pressed in a steel die at a low pressure of 50 MPa, followed by cold isostatic pressing at 250 MPa. The bar-shaped green body was debinded at 600 °C for 2 h, after which two holes for the electrodes were drilled at the opposing ends of the specimen. The green body was then pre-sintered in a muffle furnace at 1000 °C for 10 h to increase handling strength, increase neck size between contacting particles, and remove residual chlorine impurities [15]. The distance between the holes was 20 mm, and the cross-section of the green body was approximately 5.6×3.6 mm. The green body was connected to the power supply using metallic wire electrodes. The sections of the electrodes in direct contact with the specimen were made of Pt. In addition, Pt paste was painted around the electrodes, including the drilled holes as shown in Ref. [27].

Flash sintering was performed in air in a modified box furnace at a furnace temperature of 900 °C. A DC power supply (EA-PSI 9750-60; EA Elektro-Automatik GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) was used for the experiments. Flash sintering was initiated under voltage control by applying an electric field of 60 V/cm. During the flash event [32], the power supply was switched to current control, and the current was increased by steps. The first current limit was 0.4 A, and this was then increased by 0.4 A every 30 s until the final current limit of 2.4 A was reached. The dwell time at the final current limit was 2 min. For comparison, a sample from the same 3YSZ green body was prepared by a rapid sintering technique (also known as fast firing) that did not involve the flow of electric current through the sample. The process was carried out in an elevator furnace as described in a previous study [33]. A heating rate of ~ 300 °C/min was applied from 900 °C up to 1525 °C followed by 30 s dwell time and rapid cooling back to 900 °C. The flash sintered sample is denoted as “FS” in the following text, while the rapidly sintered sample is denoted as “RS”. Both sintered samples were cut along a longitudinal axis and mechanically polished using diamond polishing paste down to 0.25 μm to observe the microstructure.

To assess the overall phase composition, X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were carried out on polished cross-sections of the as-sintered ceramics. The XRD measurements were performed in the Bragg-Brentano configuration using Cu K α radiation with a wavelength of $\lambda = 1.540562 \text{ \AA}$. A thin Ni foil was used as an effective Cu K β filter. The measurement region was defined using a 2 mm incident slit to attenuate spill-over of incident radiation that could potentially produce diffraction artefacts. The area of interest corresponded to the region with the highest incidence of abnormal grains. Diffraction patterns were collected in the 2θ range from 10° to 90° . The data were analysed using PDXL2 software. Rietveld refinement was performed using a database to refine the phase compositions of sintered samples. For phase identification, .cif files with ICSD code 38870 (monoclinic zirconia) and ICSD code 655671 (tetragonal zirconia) were used.

Raman spectroscopy was used as a complementary technique to XRD. The measurements were performed on a confocal Raman microscope (Alpha 300R, WITec) using a green excitation laser with a wavelength of 532 nm and Zeiss objective (EC Epiplan-Neofluar Dic 50x / 0.8). Raman spectra were acquired using a laser power of 25 mW with an integration time of 5 s per accumulation over 30 accumulations. Multiple areas were analysed in the region of the FS sample known to contain abnormal grains. The measurements were evaluated using reference data for the Raman peak positions of *c*, *t*, and *m* phases reported by Ramos et. al. [34].

The microstructures of polished as sintered cross-sections were investigated using electron microscopy. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM; Verios 460L, FEI, Czechia) was performed on carbon-coated samples with an amorphous carbon layer of approximately 15 nm to suppress charging effects. The grains were visualized without thermal etching of the sample unless otherwise stated. Channelling contrast was used to reveal individual grains and the differences in their crystal orientation. To enhance channelling contrast, a solid-state annular back-scattered electron detector was used in combination with an acceleration voltage of 30 kV and a beam current of 3.2 nA.

Grain size was estimated using the linear intercept method from SEM images of polished and thermally etched surfaces, following the ASTM E1382 standard. The thermal etching protocol was as follows: heating at a rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to $1200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a dwell time of 15 min. The linear intercept grain size

was multiplied by 1.56 to obtain the true grain size [35]. The mean value with confidence interval ($\alpha = 0.05$) is reported in the text. Two types of grain sizes were determined: the size of abnormal grains and the grain size of the fine-grained matrix.

Vickers indentation (THV-30MD, Shanghai Test Instrument Co., Ltd, China) was used to study the effect of local stress fields on the behaviour of abnormal grains in the as-sintered material. A load of 10 kg (HV10) was applied. The indent was placed near a region containing abnormal grains. The region around a crack propagating from the corner of the indent into an abnormal grain was examined to assess the transformability.

The microanalysis of phase composition at the grain level in the as-sintered FS sample and the effect of local stress fields on phase stability were investigated using transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Three TEM lamellae were extracted from different regions of the flash sintered sample using a focused ion beam (FIB; Helios NanoLab G3, FEI, Czechia): (i) a region containing abnormal grains, (ii) a region of the fine-grained submicron matrix, and (iii) a region containing the interface between an abnormal grain and the surrounding submicron matrix intersected by an indentation-induced crack. Polished, carbon-coated samples were used. An additional 3 μm thick carbon protective layer was deposited in situ using a gas injection system to eliminate possible surface phase changes caused by ion-sample interaction. Final FIB polishing was performed at 5 kV. The final thickness of the TEM lamellae was below 100 nm. Prior to TEM analysis, the samples were examined using a STEM detector in the SEM (Helios NanoLab G3, FEI, Czechia).

TEM analyses of the prepared TEM lamellae were carried out using several microscopes: Titan Themis (FEI, Czechia) operated at 300 kV, Talos 200i (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Czechia) operated at 200 kV, JEOL JEM F200 (JEOL, Japan) operated at 200 kV, and an aberration-corrected JEOL ARM200CF (JEOL, USA) operated at 200 kV. Overview images were acquired in scanning TEM (STEM) mode using bright field (BF), dark field (DF), and high-angle annular dark field (HAADF) detectors. The camera length was set to 73 mm. The collection angles for the respective detectors were as follows: 16 mrad for BF, 19–72 mrad for DF, and 76–200 mrad for HAADF. Before orienting the sample along specific zone axes, convergent beam electron diffraction (CBED) patterns were acquired at a camera

length of 99 mm to assess the local crystallographic orientation. Final selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns were recorded in TEM mode using a 40 μm selected area aperture and a camera length of 360 mm. The electron diffraction patterns were analysed using the CrysTBox tool [36]. A 4D STEM dataset was recorded using the smallest condenser aperture, while the convergence angle was manually adjusted by changing the focus of the C3 lens. The dataset size was 75×70 pixels with a pixel size of approximately 28 nm. The diffraction patterns were recorded with a size of 1024×1024 pixels and binned by a factor of two during post-processing.

Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis was conducted using a SuperX G2 detector system (Bruker) integrated into a Titan Themis microscope operated at 300 kV. The screen current during acquisition was 550 pA. The measurements were carried out in STEM mode. Elemental maps and point analyses were acquired at a dispersion of 5 eV per channel. The data were processed and analysed using the integrated Velox software. Quantification of elemental compositions in at.% was performed using absorption correction (a generalized form of Cliff–Lorimer quantification), based on a TEM lamella thickness of 100 nm and a material density of 6.1 g/cm^3 . The step size (sampling pitch) was 2.705 nm per pixel, and each line profile spanned approximately 400 nm, corresponding to 148 measurement points (148 pixels). The line profiles were extracted in Velox using an integration window of 150 pixels to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. For the high-resolution line EDX analysis shown in Fig. 7, the line length was 185 pixels, corresponding to approximately 215 nm, i.e. a step size of about 1.16 nm per point along the line. The profile displayed was extracted using an integration width of 62 pixels (Velox) to improve the signal-to-noise ratio.

3. Results

The XRD patterns indicate a t phase composition for both the FS and RS samples (Fig. 1); no additional peaks corresponding to the m phase (Fig. 1 (a)) or the c phase (Fig. 1 (b)) were observed. No preferential crystallographic orientation was detected in the samples based on the XRD measurements. In the case of the FS sample, asymmetric peak broadening can be observed (Fig. 1 (c)), particularly in the region of the most intense tetragonal reflection, $t_1 = (101)_t$. Using Rietveld refinement, the unit cell parameters for the RS sample were determined as $a = 3.61 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 5.17 \text{ \AA}$. The FS sample exhibited the same values.

Raman spectroscopy was used as a complementary technique to confirm the t phase composition. No Raman bands corresponding to the m phase were detected in either the FS or RS samples. Both spectra were characterized by five distinct peaks corresponding to the t phase, in agreement with the XRD results (Fig. 2).

Figure 1 (a) XRD patterns of FS and RS samples. The positions of the tetragonal phase peaks (t) are marked in black, while the theoretical positions of the prominent monoclinic phase peaks (m) are marked in red. (b) Detail demonstrating the absence of reflections corresponding to the cubic phase (c), whose theoretical peak position is indicated in blue. (c) Detail of the asymmetric broadening of the $t_1 = (101)_t$ reflection in the FS sample.

Figure 2 Raman spectra of the FS sample and RS samples. The theoretical positions of Raman peaks corresponding to the monoclinic phase are indicated in red.

The microstructure of the RS sample was composed of a fine-grained matrix with no signs of AGG (Fig. 3). In contrast, the microstructure of the FS sample consisted of a fine-grained matrix with embedded abnormal grains (Fig. 4). These abnormal grains were confined to the interior region of the sample located between the cathode and anode, corresponding to the oxygen-deficient region, as indicated by the dark colouring of the material. Differences in channelling contrast were observed within the abnormal grains, revealing subregions with different crystallographic orientations within grains that appear macroscopically uniform. The abnormal grains also contained entrapped pores. Compared to the fine-grained matrix, the occurrence of entrapped pores was higher within the abnormal grains. The average grain size of the abnormal grains was $53 \mu\text{m} \pm 5 \mu\text{m}$, whereas the average grain size of the fine-grained matrix was $0.77 \mu\text{m} \pm 0.12 \mu\text{m}$. In contrast, the RS sample exhibited a uniform grain size with an average value of $0.31 \mu\text{m} \pm 0.03 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 3 Microstructure of the RS sample with homogeneous microstructure, free of abnormal grains.

Figure 4 Detail of abnormal grains in the FS sample. Channelling contrast revealed a non-trivial sub-grain structure within the abnormal grains. Black dots correspond to pores.

The region containing abnormal grains with visible differences in channelling contrast was further examined by TEM; a higher magnification image is shown in Fig. 5. Fine crystallographically oriented lamellar structures can be observed within the grains. TEM examination also revealed the presence of additional internal boundaries within the abnormal grains. The positions of the grain boundaries are marked by white dashed lines in Fig. 5. The sample was tilted to the pole of grain G1. By fitting the diffraction pattern from G1 using reference data for tetragonal zirconia ($P4_2/nmc$ space group), the beam direction was indexed as $[\bar{1}\bar{1}1]_t$. Small deviations from the G1 pole observed for grains G2 and G3 in the small out-of-centre shift of Kikuchi diffraction patterns from G2 and G3 (see Supplementary Fig. S1) indicate that their crystallographic orientations differ by up to 5° from that of G1. The corresponding SAED patterns are shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5 BF-STEM image of an abnormal grain showing internal sub-grain boundaries (indicated by white dashed lines). Diffraction patterns were acquired along the $[\bar{1}\bar{1}1]_t$ zone axis of G1. Bright features in G1 and G2 correspond to entrapped pores.

The lattice parameters derived from the SAED were $a = 3.61 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 5.17 \text{ \AA}$, identical to those obtained from the XRD measurements. EDX analysis of the chemical composition in the region of shown in Fig. 5 revealed differences in composition between individual grains G1, G2, and G3 (Fig. 6). However, within each grain the chemical composition was largely homogeneous on the scale of these measurements (probe size 2.7 nm), with only small local deviations, as shown by the line profiles in Fig. 6. The ideal composition of 3YSZ ($Zr_{0.94}Y_{0.06}O_{1.97}$) corresponds to a Zr/O ratio of 0.48. In the present case, the measured Zr/O ratios for G1, G2 and G3 were 0.52, 0.63, and 0.48, respectively. The mean concentrations of yttrium and zirconium in these grains were $(2.5 \pm 0.2) \text{ at.}\%$ and $(34.2 \pm 1.0) \text{ at.}\%$, respectively. No statistically significant differences in yttrium concentration were observed between grains G1, G2, and G3 (Fig. 6). The measured Y/Zr ratio of 0.07 is close to the nominal value of 0.06. For comparison, the Zr/O ratio in the unreduced RS sample was 0.52, with yttrium, zirconium and oxygen concentrations of (2.0 ± 0.3) , (33.5 ± 1.7) and (64.5 ± 1.7) , respectively.

Figure 6 STEM-EDX analysis of abnormal grains G1, G2 and G3 shown in Fig. 5. (a) BF-STEM image of the analysed region; the lines indicate the positions of the EDX line profiles. The purple rectangle marks the region analysed in detail in Fig. 7. (b-d) Elemental distributions of yttrium, zirconium and oxygen, respectively.

Chemical analysis using step size of 1.2 nm at the sub-grain scale revealed a modulated yttrium distribution in all abnormal grains studied, as shown in Fig. 7. This modulation corresponds to the lamellar structure observed by STEM in Fig. 5. The spacing of the lamellae was approximately 30–40 nm. Detailed analysis of grain G2 showed that the mean concentration of yttrium in the Y-rich zones reached (4.2 ± 0.6) at.% with a peak value of about 4.8 at.%, whereas the mean concentration of yttrium in the Y-lean zones was (2.2 ± 0.5) at.% with the lowest measured concentration below 2.0 at.% (Fig. 7). The combined mean yttrium concentration of the Y-rich and Y-lean zones was (2.5 ± 0.2) at.%. The mean concentrations of zirconium and oxygen in the Y-rich and Y-lean zones were comparable and generally constant along the analysed line profile, with no statistically significant differences between the zones (Fig. 7), although small local fluctuations in zirconium and oxygen concentrations were observed.

Figure 7 Detailed analysis of the region marked by the purple rectangle in Fig. 6. (a) HAADF-STEM image of the area of interest showing the modulated structure; line D indicates the path of the EDX line profile. (b-d) Elemental distributions of yttrium, zirconium and oxygen, respectively.

The chemical composition of the fine-grained matrix is shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. Yttrium segregation was observed in the matrix, occurring either in the form of yttrium clustering, similar to that previously reported for coarsened 3YSZ [3], or, in some grains, as a modulated pattern comparable to that observed in the abnormal grains (Fig. 10). The mean value of yttrium concentration in the fine-grained matrix was (2.7 ± 0.5) at.%, comparable to the values measured in the abnormal grains (Fig. 6, Fig. 7). The fine-grained matrix was also reduced, with a mean Zr/O atomic ratio of 0.58. Detailed chemical analysis of a single grain from the fine-grained matrix revealed several regions of yttrium segregation within the grain (Fig. 9). The mean yttrium concentration in this grain was (2.9 ± 0.5) at.%, while the Zr/O atomic ratio was 0.61, similar to the mean value for the fine-grained matrix (Fig. 8).

Figure 8 STEM-EDX analysis of the fine-grained matrix (detail). (a) HAADF-STEM image of the analysed region with the position of the EDX line scan indicated. (b-d) Elemental distributions of yttrium, zirconium and oxygen, respectively. (e) Yttrium concentration profile along the line scan.

Figure 9 STEM-EDX analysis of the fine-grained matrix (detail). (a) HAADF-STEM image of the analysed region with the position of the EDX line scan indicated. (b-d) Elemental distributions of yttrium, zirconium and oxygen, respectively. (e) Yttrium concentration profile along the line scan.

Figure 10 HAADF-STEM image of a fine-grained matrix grain showing a modulated structure (indicated by red arrows).

The effect of mechanical stress on the stability of the t phase in abnormal grains was investigated using a TEM lamella containing a Vickers indentation-induced crack (Fig. 11 (a)). The lamella contained an abnormal grain (Fig. 11 (b)) and the surrounding fine-grained matrix (Fig. 11 (c)). The crack induced a phase transformation in both the abnormal grain and the fine-grained matrix. This resulted in a needle-like microstructure characteristic of the $t \rightarrow m$ transformation in 3YSZ. The occurrence of the $t \rightarrow m$ transformation was confirmed by analysis of the SAED patterns (Fig. 11 (d), (g)). The region of the abnormal grain unaffected by the propagating crack retained tetragonal symmetry (Fig. 11 (d) Diff 1). Near the crack, the diffraction pattern (Fig. 11(e) Diff 2) contained reflections from the original t phase (Diff 1). Additional diffraction spots corresponding to forbidden reflections of the t phase appeared, together with a new set of diffraction spots (marked with green oval) attributable to the m phase. The transformation of the abnormal grain to the m phase was further supported by 4D-STEM measurements, which allowed the orientation of the monoclinic needles to be unambiguously determined (Fig. 12, (c), (d)). Grains of the fine-grained matrix unaffected by the propagating crack retained tetragonal symmetry (Fig. 11 (f) Diff 3 and Fig. 12 (b), (e)). In contrast, SAED patterns obtained from the crack-affected fine-grained matrix exhibited a powder-like diffraction pattern consisting of multiple sets of reflections including some from m phase, resulting from the relatively large selected-area aperture (Fig. 11(g) Diff 4).

Figure 11 TEM analysis of crack-induced transformation in the FS sample. (a) BF-STEM image of the TEM lamella containing a crack. The position of the SAED pattern Diff 3 acquired from a crack-unaffected matrix grain is marked with a white circle. (b) Detail of (a) showing the positions of SAED patterns Diff 1 and Diff 2, corresponding to an abnormal grain unaffected by crack propagation and an abnormal grain affected by crack propagation, respectively (red and green circles). (c) Detail of (a) showing the position of SAED pattern Diff 4 acquired from a crack-affected matrix grain (yellow circle). (d) SAED pattern from Diff 1. (e) SAED pattern from Diff 2. Red circles mark diffraction spots corresponding to those observed in (d); teal circles indicate forbidden reflections from the $[301]_t$ zone axis caused by a strain introduced into the material due to crack propagation. The green oval marks additional diffraction spots related to crack-induced transformation. (f) SAED from Diff 3. (g) SAED pseudo powder diffraction from Diff 4 where some diffractions are attributed to monoclinic phase.

Figure 12 (a) Bright field image of lamella with areas of 4D STEM diffraction analysis marked - 1, 2, 3 and 4. (B) and (e) confirms tetragonal symmetry of abnormal grain, (c) and (d) confirms monoclinic phase near a propagating crack induced by stress field around the crack.

4. Discussion

4.1 Grain size distribution and grain morphology

Both rapid sintering and flash sintering produced highly dense 3YSZ samples, but with significantly different grain size distributions. Rapid sintering resulted in a uniform microstructure with a monomodal grain size distribution and an average grain size of $\sim 0.3 \mu\text{m}$, consistent with previously reported studies [33,37]. In contrast, flash sintering produced a bimodal grain size distribution consisting of a sub-

micrometric matrix containing a small number of very large grains. It is well-known that the grain size distribution in DC flash sintered 3YSZ is often non-uniform due to several factors: (1) a non-uniform temperature profile caused by inside-out heating, which leads to faster grain growth in the sample's core compared with the surface [38,39], (2) electrochemical reduction, which accelerates grain growth in oxygen-deficient regions [21–24], and (3) exaggerated grain growth at the sample-electrode interface caused by extremely high temperatures resulting from high contact resistance [25,26]. Factors (1) and (2) rarely produce grains larger than a few μm , and the accelerated grain growth associated with factor (3) can be mitigated by modifying the electrode design and applying conductive pastes to reduce contact resistance, as was done in this work. The calculated temperature of the flash sintered sample was 1600°C (using black body radiation model [12], emissivity 0.9 [40])

Reports of 3YSZ grains larger than $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ in the flash-sintering literature are typically associated with studies investigating extreme sintering conditions. However, none of these studies – except the present work and our previous study [27] – have documented abnormal grain growth (AGG) in 3YSZ, i.e. the occurrence of a small number of abnormally large grains within an otherwise fine-grained, sub-micrometric matrix. For example, in Ref. [21], grains comparable in size to the abnormal grains observed in the present study were found in the cathodic region of DC-loaded 3YSZ. There was, however, no bimodal distribution, meaning that all the grains in the cathodic region were relatively large, while all the grains in the anodic region were relatively small. In that case, however, no bimodal grain size distribution was present: grains in the cathodic region were uniformly large, whereas grains in the anodic region remained relatively small. This behaviour was attributed to accelerated grain growth kinetics in the oxygen-deficient cathodic region, implying that AGG did not occur. Instead, the large grains resulted from uniform grain coarsening enabled by a high diffusion rate, elevated temperature, and long dwell time.

The reason for the formation of AGG under the stepped loading conditions in this work and reference [27] is not clear but it is worth noting that it is uniquely associated with DC flash sintering, as there are no mentions of abnormal grain growth in the AC flash sintering literature to date, nor in the context of

any other rapid sintering techniques. It may, therefore, relate to the electrochemical reduction occurring during DC flash sintering.

The crystallographic contrast observed in SEM suggests the presence of crystallographic twins and/or low-angle grain boundaries within the abnormal grains (Fig. 4), consistent with EBSD results reported previously [27]. Consequently, grain sizes determined using conventional methods such as thermal etching should be interpreted with caution, as it is difficult to clearly define a single grain using this approach. Nevertheless, even regions exhibiting homogeneous contrast – indicative of uniform crystallographic orientation – exceed the stability size limit of the t phase in 3YSZ [1,5]. At the same time, the characteristic microstructure associated with the $t \rightarrow m$ transformation was not observed.

This transformation typically produces a needle-like microstructure within the original tetragonal grains, as reported in other studies of 3YSZ materials [4,41,42]. In addition, clusters of pores were frequently observed within the abnormal grains. This likely reflects rapid grain-boundary migration during flash sintering, during which pores were unable to migrate with the moving grain boundaries and consequently became trapped within the abnormal grains. All observed abnormal grains exhibited similar microstructural characteristics regardless of their location within the sample (anode side, cathode side, or central region).

4.2 Global phase and elemental composition

If we focus on the results describing the phase composition of the FS sample globally (XRD and Raman spectroscopy), it is evident that despite the presence of abnormal grains, no characteristic signal of the m phase was detected, and the overall phase composition of the material remained tetragonal (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2). This indicates that the m phase was either absent in the FS sample, not present at the analysed locations, or present below the detection limit of the analytical techniques. Since the analyses were performed in regions containing the highest concentration of abnormal grains, which extended over a substantial area of the polished cross-section, the second possibility can be considered unlikely. The third possibility can also be ruled out, as the m phase has previously been detected by these techniques in amounts as low as 1% [3,41], which is significantly lower than the estimated volume fraction of abnormal grains in the microstructure.

The absence of the *m* phase despite the presence of exceptionally large grains in flash-sintered 3YSZ has also been reported by Dong et al. [21] and more recently by Ong et al. [24] who suggested the possible formation of the non-transformable tetragonal (*t'*) phase as a result of electrical loading and electrochemical reduction of 3YSZ. However, detailed information about the microstructure and properties of these grains was not provided. The *c* phase was also not detected. The characteristic diffraction peak of the *c* (or near-cubic) symmetry is absent at high diffraction angles, while a fully developed tetragonal peak splitting is observed (Fig. 1(b)). The asymmetric peak broadening observed in Fig. 1(c) is most likely an artefact of polishing rather than a feature of the flash-sintered material, as it appears only at low diffraction angles where the penetration depth of the incident X-rays is limited to the near-surface region of the sample.

The diffraction pattern obtained from grain G1 is in good agreement with that expected for a tetragonal crystal lattice viewed along the $[\bar{1}\bar{1}1]_t$ zone axis (Fig. 5). The lattice parameters derived from the electron diffraction were $a = 3.61 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 5.17 \text{ \AA}$, identical to those obtained from the XRD measurements. Therefore, the electron diffraction analysis fully supports the XRD results, confirming the tetragonal symmetry of the abnormal grains.

Since yttrium doping is responsible for stabilizing the tetragonal structure, STEM-EDX analysis of the elemental composition was performed (Fig. 6). At the grain level, the abnormal grains contained between (2.3 ± 0.2) at.% of yttrium for grain G3 and (2.7 ± 0.2) at.% of yttrium for grain G2. No segregation of yttrium was detected along grain boundaries, unlike in conventionally sintered 3YSZ where grain-boundary segregation has been reported by Matsui et al. [43]. The measured yttrium concentrations appear slightly higher than expected for the starting powder, as 3YSZ should contain approximately 2 at.% yttrium with a Y/Zr ratio of 0.06. The mean calculated Y/Zr ratio in the abnormal grains was 0.07 ± 0.01 (calculated using propagation of uncertainty), which is close to the nominal value. Therefore, in terms of cation composition, the yttrium content of the grains remains comparable to that of the starting material. The apparent discrepancy in the overall elemental composition can be partially explained by oxygen reduction of the material during flash sintering. Even though EDX results support the claim only for G2 and in other grains the reduction was not supported by direct measurement the

black colouring of the FS sample is strong evidence for some level of material reduction. The reduction observed in the FS sample is consistent with previously reported studies on electrochemically reduced zirconia. The reduction observed in the FS sample is consistent with previously reported studies on electrochemically reduced zirconia [18, 27].

4.3 Nano-scale yttrium modulation mechanism and stability of tetragonal phase

A detailed analysis of grain G2 (Fig. 7) revealed modulation of yttrium at the nanoscale (Fig. 7 (b)), resulting in chemical inhomogeneity within the abnormal grains manifested by alternating Y-lean and Y-rich regions. The yttrium signal follows the contrast observed in the HAADF image, reflecting the dependence of HAADF contrast on the average atomic number of the material. Charge neutrality of the material is most likely maintained by local fluctuations in the zirconium and oxygen concentrations, which were too small to be detected against the high global concentrations of these elements.

An inevitable consequence of yttrium modulation should be a change in tetragonality, where a phase closer in symmetry to the c phase alternates with a phase of higher tetragonality. The lamellar microstructure observed in Fig. 7 is similar in both appearance and origin to the microstructure reported by Krogstad et al. after thermal aging of ~ 4 mol% yttria-stabilized zirconia (4YSZ) EB-PVD thermal barrier coatings [44]. These coatings initially have a uniform yttrium distribution in a non-transformable tetragonal (t') phase. t' is a compositionally uniform tetragonal phase with the same crystal structure as the equilibrium t phase but is supersaturated in yttria and therefore metastable in the $t + c$ region of the phase diagram with respect to decomposition to the equilibrium t composition, with lower yttrium content, and an yttrium-rich c phase. Krogstad et al. showed that this decomposition, which is sluggish due to the low lattice diffusion coefficients for cations in zirconia, occurs by a mechanism consistent with spinodal decomposition, initially forming a modulated, coherent microstructure of Y-rich and Y-lean regions strikingly similar to ours (Fig. 7).

t' is most often identified as a phase formed during rapid cooling of an equilibrium c phase from typical temperatures of ~ 2100 °C to below the $T_0(c/t)$ temperature, whereupon a displacive transformation from c to t takes place [45]. The distortions involved lead to a characteristic structure of twinned domains [46]. It is important to recognise that the lamellar structures seen in this work do *not* represent such

domains. Not only do the samples not reach the temperatures required to transform completely to c , but also the structures we observe are finer than the quenched domain structures and, crucially, show strong modulations in yttrium content, whereas t' domains are of uniform composition.

The t' phase forms without the twinned domain structure in EB-PVD coatings such as those studied by Krogstad et al. because the YSZ is deposited from the vapour phase at temperatures ~ 1000 °C, well below $T_0(c/t)$, thus avoiding any displacive transformation. Single domain t' can also be formed by the pyrolysis of homogeneous precursors below T_0 [47]. Our materials most closely conform to this latter case. Powders with uniform composition were pre-sintered at 1000 °C, sufficient to form the tetragonal polymorph, but too low a temperature to allow significant decomposition (although the amount of decomposition indicated by published phase diagrams for 3 mol% yttria at 1000 °C is small or even zero).

The FS treatment then heated the samples rapidly to the sintering temperature of 1600–1700 °C (see Supplementary materials for temperature calculation), still below T_0 , and hot enough to allow the commencement of decomposition towards t with an yttria content of < 3 mol% and an yttria-rich c phase. Using a temperature of 1600 °C with the phase diagram of Fabrichnaya et al. [48] gives estimated yttria contents of 2.0 and 6.4 mol% yttria (Y_2O_3) for the two phases, which is in a good agreement with the experimental minimum (around 2 at.%) and maximum (around 5 at.%) values estimated using the measured cation concentrations in Fig. 7. While the t' phase in thermal barrier coatings is relatively stable under normal operating conditions, the higher temperatures during flash sintering used in our study would immediately initiate decomposition. Nevertheless, the dwell times are so short and the heating and cooling so rapid that only the beginnings of the decomposition occur and the microstructure remains very fine. In these early stages, the constraint between the coherent lamellae prevents the two compositions from taking up their stress-free lattice parameters, causing the structure to appear as a single tetragonal phase in diffraction studies [44].

The phase diagram suggests that the amount of the Y-rich composition (near cubic phase) should be small for our lower yttria content (3 mol%) but it has been suggested previously [30,43] that the effect of oxygen vacancies on phase content of electrochemically reduced of YSZ is similar to that of adding

more Y^{3+} , particularly if charge compensation is maintained by reducing Zr^{4+} to Zr^{3+} . In this way, the equilibrium phase composition under DC flash sintering conditions of oxygen-reduced abnormal grains would more closely resemble higher yttria content compositions such as 4YSZ.

The stability with respect to transformation to m phase at room temperature is attributed to the lamellar coherency and oxygen vacancies, as described by Krogstad et al. [44], and the small size of the Y-lean lamellae, as well as the usual additional constraint from the surrounding material. The thermal aging of 4YSZ leads to lamellar coarsening [44], where the Y-lean lamellae will eventually coarsen so much that they spontaneously transform to m phase. The microstructure of the FS sample had evidently not yet reached that state, as the lamellar structure remained tetragonal after cooling, though it is susceptible to stress-induced transformation, as shown in Section 4.4. below. The related effect where the stability of the grains is not governed by the grain size but rather by the domain size of t' 3YSZ is extensively described in the work of Jue et. al [49].

The overall elemental composition of the fine-grained matrix (Fig. 8) is similar to that of the abnormal grains. In some grains, yttrium segregation in the matrix resembles the behaviour reported by Kastyl et al. [3] and Matsui et al. [43] (Fig. 9), whereas in other cases a modulated pattern of Y-rich and Y-lean regions similar to that observed in the abnormal grains is present. The occurrence of these two types of yttrium partitioning likely reflects different formation mechanisms. In the studies of Kastyl et al. [3] and Matsui et. al [43], yttrium segregation was attributed to grain growth at high sintering temperatures leading to the formation of c phase regions, as evidenced by XRD [3] and TEM [43]. In contrast, the yttrium modulation observed in the present work is most likely related to electrochemical reduction occurring during flash sintering. The uneven spatial distribution of abnormal grains may therefore originate from the inhomogeneity of the current flow during the flash event.

4.4 Stress induced transformation of abnormal grains

An important question is whether the abnormal grains retain the characteristic behaviour of conventional 3YSZ, namely the possibility of stress-induced $t \rightarrow m$ transformation during crack propagation, or whether they behave as non-transformable grains. To assess the transformability of the abnormal grains, a TEM lamella containing a Vickers indentation-induced crack intersecting both the abnormal grains

and the surrounding submicron matrix was prepared (Fig. 11(a-c)). The region around the crack exhibited features characteristic of the $t \rightarrow m$ transformation in both the abnormal grains and the fine-grained matrix (Fig. 11 (b), (c)). The observed morphology is comparable to that reported by Stastny et al. [41]. Due to the large size of the abnormal grains, the transformation zone was not constrained by grain boundaries, and the transformation region extended approximately 1 μm from the crack.

Electron diffraction patterns Diff 1 and Diff 2 demonstrate the transformation within an abnormal grain (Fig. 11 (d), (e)). Diff 1 corresponds to the tetragonal lattice of the abnormal grain with the zone axis indexed as $[301]_t$. Diff 2 contains reflections from the original tetragonal lattice together with additional diffraction spots consistent with the formation of the m phase. Reflections forbidden for the ideal tetragonal unit cell were also observed, which can be attributed to lattice distortions associated with the $t \rightarrow m$ transformation in this region of the grain.

The exact crystallographic orientation of the m phase could not be fully determined using SAED alone. Using 4D STEM on the same lamella it was confirmed that the needle-like structures spreading away from the crack are m phase and the exact crystallographic orientation of the m phase was assessed (Fig. 12). The transformation toughening mechanism is also active in the fine-grained matrix. Diffraction pattern Diff 3, obtained from a crack-unaffected grain, exhibits tetragonal symmetry with a zone axis that can be indexed close to $[1\bar{3}1]$. In contrast, the diffraction pattern obtained from a grain adjacent to the crack (Diff 4) contains multiple sets of reflections due to the small size of the transformed laths relative to the selected-area aperture. For this reason, a powder-like diffraction analysis of the SAED pattern was performed, which is consistent with the monoclinic symmetry of the transformed phase [44,50].

Summary

At first glance, the existence of abnormal tetragonal grains in DC flash sintered 3YSZ appears to be in contradiction with conventional theories that define the critical grain size limit for the t phase metastability in 3YSZ. Upon closer examination by SEM imaging, abnormal grains exhibited (low-angle) grain boundaries and possibly crystallographic twins, and TEM-EDX analysis revealed a microscopically inhomogeneous distribution of yttrium in the form of Y-lean and Y-rich lamellae,

several tens of nm in thickness. We propose that these microstructural features introduced extra stabilisation owing to the coherency and small scale of the structure, thereby maintaining the tetragonal symmetry in abnormal grains in the same way as in similar microstructures found in thermally aged EB-PVD YSZ coatings [44].

Despite these structural details, the flash sintered material remains susceptible to stress-induced tetragonal to monoclinic ($t \rightarrow m$) transformation during crack propagation, both in the abnormal grains and in the fine-grained matrix. This confirms that the main transformation toughening mechanism of 3YSZ remains functional, even in a microstructure populated by abnormal grains. In conclusion, flash sintering offers a novel route to produce 3YSZ ceramics with unconventional microstructures. These flash sintered materials may contribute to a deeper understanding of phase stability and toughening mechanisms in advanced oxide ceramics.

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Dataset availability

Dataset is available online on repository under DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15646820 and 10.5281/zenodo.15646631.

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